

Simulation for determining the rod pump system parameter values using finite difference method

Erwani Merry Sartika, Arief Darmawan

Department of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Kristen Maranatha, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Lifting petroleum to the surface requires a mechanism called an artificial lift. This mechanism is useful for increasing the flow of fluids from a well. One that uses this method is the rod pump. The rod pump system needed the appropriate design (through the determination of the value of the parameters that affect) so that the pump runs optimally. But changing the appropriate design in real terms is not economically and time-efficient. The ideal rod pump system analysis procedure is to take downhole data (in the well) which is commonly called a pump card. A pump card calculation simulation is needed to efficiently analyze the rod pump system. The wave equation can describe the model of the rod pump system. A simulation of pump data calculation is performed using the finite difference method for the wave equation solution. Through the process of tuning parameter values using trial and error methods, the steps of tuning the parameter value of the rod pump system are proposed in this paper. For further research, a pump card calculation method based on a surface card can be developed to efficiently analyze the rod pump.

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Corresponding Author:

Erwani Merry Sartika
Department of Electrical Engineering
Universitas Kristen Maranatha
Jln. Suria Sumantri 65 Bandung, Indonesia
Email: erwanimerry@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

At present, oil and gas are one of the energies that are still relied on by humans, so the demand for oil and gas is higher. However, to use it a special method is needed to transport this energy source. Therefore, to lift petroleum to the surface a mechanism called an artificial lift is needed. This mechanism is useful for increasing the flow of fluids from a well [1].

The pump is one of the industrial equipment that is widely used today, including in the oil and gas industry. Pump sucker or sucker rod pump is one type of pump in the upstream oil and gas industry that uses the method of artificial lift (power assistance) in the removal of petroleum from the well. This type of pump is usually used in wells that have particles in them and are often also applied to old wells [1]. Surface card data collection methods have been used to analyze the rod pump system. Interpretation of the actual pump conditions of the surface card is very difficult because the data are qualitative and depend on the expertise of the analyzer [2].

Therefore, an analysis procedure is used by taking downhole data (in the well) which is commonly called a pump card. A pump card calculation method based on a surface card is needed to efficiently analyze the actual pump rod system. A pump card calculation method based on a surface card is needed to be able to analyze the actual rod pump system efficiently [3]. Pump card data calculations using the finite difference method have been used to get solutions based on the wave equation [4].

Alternative system designs using simulations are carried out to get optimal results [5-8]. Through the pump card data, it is necessary to adjust the parameter values on the rod pump to obtain the ideal pump (optimal) [9]. But changing the parameter values that affect the rod pump in real terms is not economically and time-efficient [10]. Tuning parameter values is mostly done through direct data retrieval by conducting sonological tests to determine the bottom well flow pressure and reservoir pressure. Sonologists work on the principle of waves or sound from the firing or flowing of pressurized gas quickly. Redesign the sucker rod pump without changing the type of pump installed by combining the step length and pump speed, so that volumetric pumping and pump displacement efficiency are obtained based on direct data collection [11].

So, the purpose of this paper is to use simulations to determine the parameter values on the rod pump to get the ideal pump card. Through this simulation, in addition to saving costs and time, it can also be used to anticipate the rod pump if the pump card is not ideal (because it can damage the rod pump). Parameters that can be adjusted and affect the output of the rod pump system is the length of the rod string, the diameter of the rod string, and the speed of the pump [11]. Determination of the parameter value on the rod pump in advance using the trial-and-error method. Through the trial and error method, an analysis is performed to obtain the stages of determining the tuning parameters to accelerate the acquisition of parameter values (through a simulation process).

2. WORKING PRINCIPLE OF ROD PUMP

The working mechanism of the rod pump is the working process of all the components contained in the pump shown in Figure 1 [12-14]. The workings of the pump shaft are divided into two, namely on the surface and in the well. The way the rod pump works on the surface is:

- Prime motion (prime mover) will produce rotational motion, then this motion will be converted into up and down the motion by the pitman crank assembly system. Furthermore, this motion will go through a walking beam and forwarded to the horse head and made straight up and down to move the plunger inside the well.
- Pumping unit installation above the surface is connected to the pump installation in the well by the sucker rod system, so that the straight up and down motion of the horse head will be moved to the pump plunger, and the plunger will move up and down in the pump barrel.

Figure 1. Rod pump components [9]

The way the rod pump works in the well is:

- a) During an upstroke, the plunger will move upwards the traveling valve away from the standing valve, causing the traveling valve to be closed due to pressure from the fluid above it. The fluid can be lifted and out through the pipe. When the plunger moves upward, the pressure in the barrel will decrease to the vacuum pressure, so that the formation pressure will open the standing valve and the fluid will enter the barrel.
- b) During the downstroke process, the standing valve will be closed due to the pressure of the liquid above it and the influence of the weight of the balls themselves, while the traveling valve will open and be pushed by the liquid inside the barrel, then the liquid will enter the tubing and lifted due to the pump surface movement. This process will continue until the pipe is filled with fluid and moves to the surface.

3. DYNAMOMETER CARD

Dynamometer card is divided into 2 namely surface card and pump card. The surface card displays the load on the rod during the pump cycle and is converted to a pump card that displays the fluid load on the pump during the pump cycle [15-16]. The size and shape of the card show the operating conditions and pump performance as shown in Figure 2. There are 4 points, or 4 sequences that occur when lifting oil. Point 1 to 3 is during the upstroke movement and point 3 to point 1 is during the downstroke movement. Fo (fluid load on the pump) is the process of transferring the valve to fill fluid into the working barrel. Stroke length effective plunger travel (SLEPT), which is the effective stroke length to form the ideal pump card, only occurs when one valve is open and the other closed. Stroke length downhole (SLDH), which is the total stroke length of the downhole plunger [17].

The surface card is the recording of the load on the polished rod against the displacement of the position of the sucker rod which is commonly called the rod through physical sensors mounted on the polished rod. The wave equation is a mathematical model that can estimate the motion of the rod against conditions in the well [18]. A pump card is the recording of the load at the downhole against the displacement of the rod [19].

Figure 2. Surface card and pump card [17]

4. PUMP CARD

Interpretation of the actual pump conditions of surface cards is very difficult because the data are qualitative and depend on the expertise of the analyzer. The ideal analysis procedure is to take downhole data (under the well) which is commonly called a pump card. There are types of pump cards according to rod pump work and well conditions [17]:

- Ideal card: normal pump, full liquid & no gas interference. The pump is functioning properly
- Slanted: there is gas interference which causes a shift in the tubing when lifting
- Fluid pound: during downstroke there is an empty space so that it can cause the rod to break when it collides with fluid

5. THE WAVE EQUATIONS

The wave equation is ideal for representing rod movement because it involves wave propagation in continuous media. The wave equation for the rod pump is expressed by (1) [20].

$$v^2 \frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial t^2} + c \frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

In (1) is the wave equation which states that the motion of the rod is not affected by the diameter of the rod string. The wave equation that states the motion of the rod can be affected by the diameter of the rod string can be expressed in (2) [20].

$$EA \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\rho A}{144g_c} \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial t^2} + c \frac{\rho A}{144g_c} \frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

E = Modulus Young (Psi)

A = Transversal Area (inch²)

ρ = Thickness (lb / ft³)

g_c = Conversion Factor (lbm * ft / lbf / s²) = 32.2

c = damping coefficient (s⁻¹)

v = Velocity (ft / sec)

u = Rod Displacement

The finite difference method is a method for obtaining numerical solutions of partial differential equations [21]. Estimated results of wave equations are discretized using finite difference as shown in (3) [20].

$$u_{i+1,j} = \left[\frac{\alpha(1+c\Delta t)}{\beta} \right] u_{i,j+1} - \left[\frac{\alpha(2+c\Delta t)-2\beta}{\beta} \right] u_{i,j} + \frac{\alpha}{\beta} u_{i,j-1} - u_{i-1,j} \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \right) \rho A}{144g_c}$$

$$u_{0j} = g_{PRj}$$

$$\beta = \frac{EA}{\Delta x}$$

$$U_{ij} = \frac{f_{PRj} \Delta x}{EA} + U_{0,j}$$

g_{PR} = rod displacement in surface card

f_{PR} = fluid load in surface card

The final calculation for rod displacement and fluid load uses (4) and (5) [20] :

$$u_{\text{pump},j} = (1 + c\Delta t)u_{m-1,j+1} - c\Delta t u_{m-1,j} + u_{m-1,j-1} - u_{m-2,j} \quad (4)$$

$$F_{\text{pump},j} = \left(\frac{EA}{2\Delta x} \right) (3u_{m,j} - 4u_{m-1,j} + u_{m-2,j}) \quad (5)$$

U = rod displacement on pump card

F = fluid load on pump card

6. RESEARCH METHOD

In designing the pump card calculation simulation is divided into three main stages. The first step is to convert the surface card data into pump card data using the wave equation. After getting the pump card data, the parameter data that affects the rod pump system is adjusted. The last step is to analyze the results of the simulation of the rod pump system based on the pump card data.

The surface card image is taken from the database based on references as shown in Figure 3 [22]. Surface card data is in the form of data pairs X and Y, each of which has 500 points. X is the displacement data rod and Y is the data load. It is assumed that the simulation of one cycle of the rod pump system is 360 points (one full rotation of the 360° motor). Followed by making a matrix of M rows of 100, and N columns of 360 and input NaN (not a number) data to allocate initial condition data from the matrix. Initialization of

the first row and the second row of the matrix. The wave equation is used to get the next row (third row to the last row) as shown in the flow diagram of rod pump system simulation in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Surface card image[22]

Figure 4. Flow diagram of rod pump system simulation

The parameters used for pump card data calculations can be seen in Table 1. The parameters that will be used as reference parameters for the rod pump system are the parameters of rod string length, rod string diameter, and pump speed because these parameters are parameters that can be changed for the system design rod pump. The other parameters are fixed parameters that cannot be changed [23].

Figure 5 is the final result of the pump card calculation process using a wave equation that has been discretized. The column in the matrix is increased to 720 because if the calculation starts from the surface node ($i = 0$) with only one cycle until the pump solution ($i = m$) will not represent a complete cycle because to get the main calculation current data and previous data are needed. 360 data columns of the first cycle will be used as current data and previous data to be able to calculate the data that will come incomplete so that no data is lost.

The first row in the matrix is the initialization of the data displacement rod on the surface card. The second row is initializing fluid load data plus data rod displacement on the surface card. The third row to the m-row is the main calculation using the wave equation that has been discretized using finite-difference. NaN is the IEEE arithmetic representation for Not-a-Number [24]. NaN is used to allocating initial condition data from the matrix (because it cannot be a number including zero) [25].

Table 1. The parameters used for pump card calculation simulation [23]

Parameter	Description
E	Modulus Young (Psi) = $30,5 \cdot 10^6$
A	Transversal Area (inch ²) = $\pi / (4 \cdot (\text{diameter})^2)$
L	Rod String Length (ft) = Parameters to be set
v	Speed in one cycle (SPM) = Parameters to be set
D	Diameter of rod string (inch) = Parameters to be set
m	Number of matrix rows for pump card data calculation = 100
n	Number of matrix columns for calculation of pump card data = 360
c	The damping coefficient (s ⁻¹) = 0,8
ρ	Viscosity (lb / ft ³) = 490
g_c	Conversion Factor (lbm.ft/lbf/s ²) = 32.2

180x720																	
	1	2	3	...	177	178	179	180	...	541	542	543	544	...	718	719	720
1	0.0456	0.0465	0.0491	...	0.1156	0.1320	0.1501	0.1699	...	0.1914	0.1699	0.1501	0.1320	...	0.0534	0.0491	0.0465
2	0.0583	0.0592	0.0618	...	0.1284	0.1448	0.1631	0.1831	...	0.2007	0.1793	0.1596	0.1416	...	0.0652	0.0614	0.0591
3	NaN	0.0720	0.0745	...	0.1411	0.1576	0.1760	0.1963	...	0.2100	0.1887	0.1691	0.1513	...	0.0771	0.0737	NaN
4	NaN	NaN	0.0873	...	0.1539	0.1704	0.1890	0.2094	...	0.2194	0.1981	0.1786	0.1609	...	0.0889	NaN	NaN
5	NaN	NaN	NaN	...	0.1666	0.1832	0.2020	0.2226	...	0.2287	0.2076	0.1882	0.1705	...	NaN	NaN	NaN
6	NaN	NaN	NaN	...	0.1794	0.1961	0.2149	0.2358	...	0.2380	0.2170	0.1977	0.1802	...	NaN	NaN	NaN
7	NaN	NaN	NaN	...	0.1922	0.2089	0.2279	0.2490	...	0.2474	0.2264	0.2072	0.1898	...	NaN	NaN	NaN
8	NaN	NaN	NaN	...	0.2050	0.2218	0.2409	0.2622	...	0.2567	0.2358	0.2168	0.1994	...	NaN	NaN	NaN
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
178	NaN	NaN	NaN	...	14.9752	14.9682	14.9594	14.9484	...	14.9358	14.9207	14.9033	14.8840	...	NaN	NaN	NaN
179	NaN	NaN	NaN	...	NaN	14.9876	14.9787	14.9677	...	14.9549	14.9398	14.9223	NaN	...	NaN	NaN	NaN
180	NaN	NaN	NaN	...	NaN	NaN	14.9980	14.9870	...	14.9741	14.9588	NaN	NaN	...	NaN	NaN	NaN

Figure 5. Matrix for pump card calculations

7. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The parameters that influence the formation of the pump card are rod string diameter, rod string length, transverse area, density, damping factor, conversion factor, modulus young, and pump speed. In the simulation that will be tuned are the parameters of the rod string diameter, the length of the rod string, and the speed of the pump as a mechanical design and the process of the rod pump system because the other parameters are fixed coefficients. The pump card data that shows the rod pump system works well is having a large net stroke, a small stroke shift, and a large fluid load with a note that the pump card shape must resemble a rectangle (ideal pump card). Net stroke is an effective stroke to transport the fluid, if the net stroke value increases, the fluid transported will be even greater. Gross stroke is the displacement of a stroke in one pump cycle. The total stroke shift is a gross stroke reduced by a net stroke which represents a stroke that deviates from normal conditions.

In the simulation of the rod pump system, it was conducted preliminary by trial and error method by adjusting the values of the various parameters of the rod pump namely the diameter of the rod string (0.625 inches; 0.750 inches; 0.875 inches), the length of the rod string (1000 ft; 2000 ft; 3000 ft), and the speed of the rod pump in one cycle (8 SPM to 20 SPM). From all trials in Table 2, the results of simulation data are shown which are considered to be representative of all experiments.

From Table 2 the analysis of the tuning process can be concluded. In the initial tuning of the rod string diameter and the length of the rod string, one can be chosen first, because this gives the same results as the effect on the net stroke size, stroke shift, and fluid load. Small diameter rod string and long rod string will produce a large net stroke, small stroke shift, and a large enough fluid load. Meanwhile, to find out the shape of a pump card resembling a rectangle (ideal pump card) is determined by the next step which is the value of the speed of the rod pump in one cycle (SPM).

Table 2. Simulation results of pump cards with rod string diameter 0.625 inches for various rod string lengths, rod string length 3,000 feet for various rod string diameters, and pump speed 8-20 spm

Rod String Diameter (Inch)	Length of the rod string (ft)	Speed (SPM)	Net stroke (inch)	Gross Stroke (inch)	Total Stroke Shift (Inch)	Fluid load (lbs)	Length of the rod string (ft)	Rod String Diameter (Inch)	Speed (SPM)	Net stroke (inch)	Gross Stroke (inch)	Total Stroke Shift (Inch)	Fluid load (lbs)
0.625	1000	8	71,2	133,3	62,1	11730	3000	0.625	8	103,4	122,4	19	11850
		9	70,8	133,1	62,3	11930			9	104,5	120,3	15,8	12000
		10	70,5	133	62,5	11970			10	113	120,3	7,3	12200
		11	70,2	132,9	62,7	11980			11	114,4	120,8	6,4	12250
		12	69,8	132,7	62,9	12090			12	88,2	119,4	31,2	12400
		13	69,3	132,3	63	12130			13	87	118,8	31,8	12600
		14	69	131,9	62,9	12160			14	82,5	118,2	35,7	12700
		15	68,8	131,6	62,8	12200			15	83,3	117,5	34,2	12700
		16	68,7	131,5	62,8	13220			16	82,1	116,9	34,8	12800
		17	68,5	131,1	62,6	13300			17	81,5	116	34,5	13000
	18	68,3	131,2	62,9	12350	18	80,9	116,2	35,3	13200			
	19	68,2	130,9	62,7	12410	19	80,6	115,8	35,2	13500			
	20	67,5	130,6	63,1	12450	20	80,2	115,8	35,6	13750			
	8	89,8	126	36,2	11800	8	93,8	125,8	32	12200			
	9	92,8	126	30,2	12000	9	94,5	125,3	30,8	12250			
	10	93,3	125,5	30	12100	10	96,2	124,6	28,4	12350			
	11	94,7	125,3	29,6	12500	11	91,9	124,1	32,2	12500			
	12	95	125	29	12630	12	91,5	123,5	32	12750			
	13	96,3	124,7	28,4	12700	13	90,6	123	32,4	12950			
	14	96,5	124,3	27,8	12890	14	87,7	122,3	34,6	13000			
15	96,8	123,8	27	13050	15	75,4	121,5	46,1	13200				
16	83,9	123,5	39,6	13300	16	74,9	120,7	45,8	13450				
17	82,7	123	40,3	14000	17	73,5	120,3	46,8	13750				
18	81,8	122,4	40,6	14100	18	72,1	120	47,9	14100				
19	80,9	121,8	40,9	14350	19	70,3	120,1	49,8	14300				
20	80,4	121,3	40,9	14600	20	67,3	118	50,7	14850				
8	103,4	122,4	19	11850	8	79	128,8	49,8	12400				
9	104,5	120,3	15,8	12000	9	83,6	128,2	44,6	12600				
10	113	120,3	7,3	12200	10	87,4	127,6	40,2	12750				
11	114,4	120,8	6,4	12250	11	69,5	126,7	57,2	12900				
12	88,2	119,4	31,2	12400	12	72	126,3	54,3	13200				
13	87	118,8	31,8	12600	13	71	125,5	54,5	13400				
14	82,5	118,2	35,7	12700	14	70,1	124,8	54,7	13700				
15	83,3	117,5	34,2	12700	15	71	124,1	53,1	14100				
16	82,1	116,9	34,8	12800	16	71,3	123,2	51,9	14300				
17	81,5	116	34,5	13000	17	68,3	122,3	54	14800				
18	80,9	116,2	35,3	13200	18	66,2	121,7	55,5	15100				
19	80,6	115,8	35,2	13500	19	60	120,7	60,7	15400				
20	80,2	115,8	35,6	13750	20	58,5	119,8	61,3	15700				

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. (a) Pump card with a diameter of 0.625-inch rod string parameter, 2000 ft rod length, and 15 SPM speed. (b) Pump card with 0.625-inch diameter rod string parameters, 3000 ft rod length, and 11 SPM speed

Some forms of pump cards that are produced from simulations are shown in Figure 6(a) and Figure 6(b). The pump card closest to the ideal shape of the data in Table 3. is at the 15 SPM speed shown in Figure 6(a). At 0.625-inch rod string diameter, 2000 ft rod length, net stroke value was 96.8 inches, and the total stroke shift was 27 inches. In Figure 6(a) it is shown that the shape of the pump card has formed a rectangle but still needs to look for other values that have a squarer box shape (ideal pump card). The most approaching pump card the ideal shape of the data in Table 2, is at the speed of 11 SPM shown in Figure 6(b). At 0.625-inch rod string diameter, 3000 ft rod length, net stroke value is 114.4 inches, and the total stroke shift is 6.4 inches.

So the conclusion of the tuning process parameter values on the rod pump is:

- 1) Can choose the smallest rod string diameter or the longest rod string length for the initial selection of parameter values because both are linear to the net stroke:
 - a) The smaller the diameter of the rod string, the bigger the net stroke
 - b) The longer the rod string, the bigger the net stroke
- 2) If at the beginning choose the smallest rod string diameter, then select the longest rod string or if at the beginning choose the longest rod string, then select the smallest rod string diameter.
- 3) Then the speed selection (SPM) can then be adjusted from the smallest to the largest, but all conditions must be considered: first, having the largest net stroke, second having the smallest stroke shift, and the third one is having a large enough fluid load and became a square pump card (ideal pump card).

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a simulation was carried out to obtain the ideal pump card. Through the analysis of simulation results using the trial-and-error method, the tuning process of the parameter values used is to first choose the diameter of the rod string (selected small) and the length of the rod string (selected the longest), followed by the selection of the speed of the rod pump (SPM) which produces a sequence of the largest net stroke, shifting the smallest stroke, and fluid load large enough to approach the ideal shape of the pump card (rectangle). In other paper tuning parameters is done by taking data directly by performing a sonologist test to determine the bottom well flow pressure and reservoir pressure. Based on the simulation the diameter of the rod string is 0.625 inches, the length of the rod string is 3000 feet, and the pump speed of 11 SPM forms the ideal pump card. Based on the tuning process on the proposed rod pump, tuning is done by selecting the smallest rod string diameter and the longest length of the rod string, then continuing to determine the motor speed so that the most ideal pump card is obtained. For further research, a pump card calculation method based on the surface will be developed to analyze the efficiency of the rod pump. Simulation is used to adjust the rod pump parameters directly based on the surface card. In addition, further developments can take advantage of IoT for monitoring real conditions in the field (well conditions) to determine changes in parameter values that affect the performance of the rod pump system.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Erwani Merry Sartika, a lecturer in the electrical engineering study program at Universitas Kristen Maranatha. She explored the field of control systems and system identification. Her work focuses on the role of automation, modeling, and simulation.

Arief Darmawan, a graduate of the Electrical Engineering Department at Universitas Kristen Maranatha in Bandung, and his area of expertise is computer programming. He was born in 1996 in Bogor and had an internship at PT Danfoss Indonesia.